

Semiotic Analysis and Communication of Indian Mughal Paintings: An Analysis of Paintings with Flat Perspective

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Abstract: Flat perspectives are typical features of Mughal paintings expressing various meanings in different socio-cultural aspects. This research paper presents a comprehensive semiotic analysis of Indian Mughal paintings, specifically focusing on artworks employing the technique of flat perspectives. The 'Chowdhury's Semiotic Coding' technique was applied to examine the signs and symbols present in these paintings and how they relate to the compositions and elements of the artworks. Five Indian Mughal paintings with flat perspective were randomly chosen for the study, and these were evaluated by five experienced specialists from the creative industry. The research unveiled the composition and elements of the paintings related to their semiotic qualities and levels. Statistical analysis was conducted to compare the semiotic qualities of the chosen paintings, providing insights into their differences and manifestations.

Practical Implications: The results of this study offer a nuanced understanding of the cultural and communicative components present in Indian Mughal paintings with a flat perspective and contribute to our knowledge of the semiotics of Mughal paintings. This study highlights the importance of semiotic analysis as a powerful method for revealing the hidden meanings in art from different historical and cultural contexts.

Keywords: Art and aesthetic; Communication; Flat aerial perspective; Mughal landscape painting; Semiotics.

1. Introduction

In the realm of art, the brushstrokes of a painter can transcend time, culture, and perspective, offering windows into rich narratives and captivating stories (Walker, 2019). Among the diverse tapestry of artistic traditions, the Indian Mughal paintings stand as luminous testaments to a harmonious blend of aesthetics and history (Gray, 2021). The Mughal era in India, spanning from the early 16th to the mid-19th century, was a period of significant cultural and artistic flourishing. This period was marked by a remarkable fusion of cultures, creating unique art forms (Singh, 2017). Among these, Mughal paintings stand out as exquisite examples of artistic expression, offering intricate glimpses into the socio-cultural and political fabric of the time. One of the distinct features of Mughal paintings is the use of flat perspective, a technique that deviates from the traditional Western concept of depth and three-dimensionality (Subrahmanyam, 2012).

Under the support of emperors like Akbar, Jahangir, and Shah Jahan, this rich creative legacy developed and evolved into an exquisite synthesis of domestic and foreign artistic elements (Balabanlilar, 2010). These paintings, delicately crafted

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with vibrant pigments and meticulous detailing, are more than mere visual artifacts; they serve as vibrant windows into the opulent past, encapsulating the socio-cultural dynamics, courtly extravagance, and artistic prowess that defined the Mughal period (Gonzalez, 2016; Rice, 2011).

Although Mughal art has frequently been studied from stylistic and historical perspectives, a comprehensive semiotic analysis of these paintings, particularly concerning their communicative strategies, remains underdeveloped. Semiotic analysis is rooted in semiotics (or semiology), the study of signs and symbols and their use or interpretation. It explores how people derive meaning from signs and how those signs are used to communicate ideas. A sign in semiotics is anything that stands for something else, such as words, images, sounds, or gestures. Semiotic analysis involves separating these signs into their constituent parts (signifier and signified) and examining their relationships. This analysis can reveal hidden meanings, cultural contexts, and social ideologies embedded within these signs, offering a deeper understanding of their messages. Despite the aesthetic appeal and historical importance of Mughal paintings, there is minimum understanding regarding the semiotic codes embedded within paintings that employ a flat perspective. This study addresses this gap by decoding the symbolic language and cultural significance encoded in Mughal paintings that utilize a flat perspective.

The research objectives are to examine and quantify the diversity of semiotic qualities, including syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, cultural, social, and political contexts, in a specific set of Mughal artworks. To analyze and identify the unique semiotic fingerprints of individual artworks, with a focus on understanding how artistic expression and cultural influences contribute to Mughal artworks' distinctiveness. To investigate the interconnectedness of semiotic dimensions within artworks and assess how syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and social qualities interact to convey meaning and significance. To assess the influence of social and historical contexts on the semiotic expression of artworks, particularly in terms of how societal norms, authority, and historical events shape the artistic representation of Mughal artworks. To examine the role of comparative analysis in art evaluation, specifically its significance in identifying variations in semiotic qualities and uncovering subtle nuances that contribute to a deeper understanding of artworks. This research will contribute to the existing knowledge of Mughal art by offering new insights into the semiotic nuances of flat perspective in this artistic tradition.

This research is significant for art historians, cultural analysts, and enthusiasts interested in understanding the complex layers of meaning within Mughal paintings. By decoding the semiotic codes, this study contributes to scholarly discourse on Mughal art and illuminates the broader cultural exchanges among different communities during the Mughal era.

This research examines a selected number of Indian Mughal paintings that prominently feature a flat perspective. This study aims to provide a comprehensive analysis of these paintings; however, the interpretations presented are subjective and informed by available scholarly resources. This research does not encompass other forms of Mughal art, such as architecture or sculpture, and focuses specifically on paintings.

2. Literature Review

Existing studies revealed that the rich and diverse scholarship on Mughal art, specifically focusing on painting and its intersections with other forms of artistic expression, culture, and history provides insights into various aspects of Mughal painting and its significance in the broader context (Ramaswamy, 2007), examines the Mughal visual practice and its use of the globe as a symbol, offering insights into how the concept of the world and its representation were employed in Mughal artwork. (Michell, 2007; Roy, 2009), focuses on the idiosyncrasies in the late Mughal painting tradition, specifically examining the artist Mihr Chand and his contributions to Mughal art. (Koch, 2012), explores the symbolic dimensions of European cartography in Mughal allegory and history painting, highlighting the complex ways in which maps and geographical representation were integrated into Mughal visual culture. (Roy, 2012), highlights the revival of the Mughal painting tradition during the reign of Muhammad Shah, providing historical context and discussing the factors that led to this resurgence. (Rehman & Akhtar, 2012), delve into Mughal architecture, discussing its characteristics and significance in light of primary sources, contributing to the understanding of Mughal built heritage. (Rice, 2014), delves into the intertwined histories of Mughal painting and calligraphy, shedding light on how these two artistic forms influenced each other and contributed to the development of Mughal visual aesthetics. (Natif, 2015), examines the portrayal of male intimacy in a seventeenth-century Mughal illustration in the context of Renaissance painting. (Keating, 2015), explores the concept of metamorphosis in the context of the Mughal Court. The author investigates how artistic and cultural transformations occurred within the Mughal Court and how they were represented in art. (Losty, 2017), explores a collection of eighteenth-century Mughal paintings from the Swinton collection, potentially discussing the provenance, artistic styles, and historical context of these artworks. (Asgahr, Yaseen, & Nadeem, 2023), focus on the use of gold in Mughal miniature court paintings during the reign of Emperor Shah Jahan. (Saviello, 2019), explores the Western tableaux in Mughal painting, highlighting their role as paradigms of the emperor's perfect vision and the transcultural aspects of Mughal artistic representation. (Szántó, 2019), discusses Mughal painting's connections with Persia and Europe. The study

explores the global influences on Mughal art and how it intersected with other artistic traditions. (Khera, 2013), focuses on Mughal paintings depicting hunting scenes and the portrayal of aristocracy within these artworks including exploring the artistic representation of hunting as a royal pastime in Mughal culture and may analyze the symbolism and stylistic aspects of such paintings. (Calabria, 2021), focuses on a specific aspect of Mughal painting decapitations and examines whether they were depicted as acts of persecution or punishment. This topic delves into the portrayal of violence in Mughal art and its potential cultural and symbolic significance, making it relevant for those interested in the interpretation of violent imagery in these paintings. (Mokhtar et al. 2022), present a contemporary perspective on Mughal miniature paintings, emphasizing their importance in art appreciation and their presence in the Islamic Art Museum Malaysia. (Mumtaz, 2023), present the understanding of imperial Mughal painting in the context of religious symbolism and allegory. (Koch, 2023), explores the historiography of Mughal painting discovery in Vienna, particularly through the work of Josef Strzygowski and his circle. (Saviello, 2023), examines the interplay between European and Mughal artistic and cultural influences, potentially shedding light on how Mughal spirituality and artistic traditions were portrayed in European contexts. (Analojeh, 2023), conducts a comparative analysis of paintings depicting women from both the Safavid and Mughal eras, potentially exploring the similarities and differences in artistic representation, symbolism, and cultural contexts.

By exploring the complex meaning and communication possibilities hidden within the flat perspective of Indian Mughal art, our research seeks to close this gap. This study's main goal is to do a semiotic analysis of Indian Mughal paintings, with an emphasis on those that use flat perspective, to reveal the semiotic codes and norms built into flat perspective in Indian Mughal paintings, finding out how these pieces of art express rich meanings and tales through the interaction of symbols, composition, and viewpoint. Describe how the cultural, religious, and societal circumstances of the Mughal creative heritage influenced the development and understanding of flat perspective.

3. Methodology

The research applied Chowdhury's (Chowdhury & Varala, 2023) Semiotic Coding method (see Table 1) to investigate the semiotic elements embedded within paintings and scrutinize their associations with the compositions and elements present in the artworks. To conduct this study, five specific Indian Mughal paintings featuring flat perspectives were selected. To ensure a comprehensive analysis, five specialists, each with a minimum of ten years of experience in the creative industry, participated in the evaluation process. The demographic profile of these experts revealed an average age of 42.5 years, with male experts making up 60% of the panel. Employing Chowdhury's Semiotic Coding technique, these experts conducted a meticulous examination and interpretation of the semiotic characteristics prevalent in the chosen paintings. This intricate process involved the identification and elucidation of the signs, symbols, and visual cues employed within the artworks to convey meaning and cultural significance. Statistical comparisons were made among the semiotic quality-related factors of the five selected paintings using SPSS followed through a chi-square test and Z-test based on scores given by experts. The outcomes of the statistical analysis are detailed in this article, providing valuable perspectives on the distinctions in semiotic expressions among these artworks.

Table 1. Sample of Chowdhury’s Semiotic Quality Analysis of a Painting (P-1).

Metrics	Attributes	Painting Composition
Syntactic quality (S) $SL \times b_{s1} + SR \times b_{s2}$	= Lawfulness Richness	$SL \times b_{sl,2} + SR \times b_{sr,2}$
Semantic quality (E) $EI \times b_{e1} + EC \times b_{e2} + EL \times b_{e3}$	= Interpretability Consistency Clarity	$EI \times b_{el,3} + EC \times b_{ec,2} + EL \times b_{e3,2}$
Pragmatic quality (P) $PC \times b_{p1} + PA \times b_{p2} + PR \times b_{p3}$	= Comprehensiveness Accuracy Relevance	$PC \times b_{p1,2} + PA \times b_{p2,2} + PR \times b_{p2,3}$
Social quality (O) $OA \times b_{o1} + OB \times b_{o2}$	= Authority History	$OA \times b_{ol,3} + OB \times b_{ob,3}$
Overall quality (OQ)	$\sum \{(SL \times b_{sl,2} + SR \times b_{sr,2}) + (EI \times b_{el,3} + EC \times b_{ec,2} + EL \times b_{e3,2}) + (PC \times b_{p1,2} + PA \times b_{p2,2} + PR \times b_{p2,3}) + (OA \times b_{ol,3} + OB \times b_{ob,3})\}$	

Wight 1: Poor; 2: Moderate; 3: Good

Table 2. Overall Semiotic Quality of all Selected Paintings.

Paintings	Semiotic Codes for Overall Quality
P-1	$\sum \{(SL \times b_{sl.2} + SR \times b_{s2.2}) + (EI \times b_{el.3} + EC \times b_{e2.2} + EL \times b_{e3.2}) + (PC \times b_{p1.2} + PA \times b_{p2.2} + PR \times b_{p2.3}) + (OA \times b_{ol.3} + OB \times b_{o2.3})\}$
P-2	$\sum \{(SL \times b_{sl.2} + SR \times b_{s2.2}) + (EI \times b_{el.2} + EC \times b_{e2.2} + EL \times b_{e3.2}) + (PC \times b_{p1.2} + PA \times b_{p2.2} + PR \times b_{p2.3}) + (OA \times b_{ol.3} + OB \times b_{o2.3})\}$
P-3	$\sum \{(SL \times b_{sl.2} + SR \times b_{s2.2}) + (EI \times b_{el.2} + EC \times b_{e2.2} + EL \times b_{e3.2}) + (PC \times b_{p1.2} + PA \times b_{p2.2} + PR \times b_{p2.2}) + (OA \times b_{ol.2} + OB \times b_{o2.3})\}$
P-4	$\sum \{(SL \times b_{sl.2} + SR \times b_{s2.2}) + (EI \times b_{el.2} + EC \times b_{e2.2} + EL \times b_{e3.2}) + (PC \times b_{p1.2} + PA \times b_{p2.2} + PR \times b_{p2.2}) + (OA \times b_{ol.2} + OB \times b_{o2.2})\}$
P-5	$\sum \{(SL \times b_{sl.2} + SR \times b_{s2.2}) + (EI \times b_{el.2} + EC \times b_{e2.2} + EL \times b_{e3.2}) + (PC \times b_{p1.2} + PA \times b_{p2.2} + PR \times b_{p2.2}) + (OA \times b_{ol.3} + OB \times b_{o2.3})\}$

Wight 1: Poor; 2: Moderate; 3: Good

4. Result and Findings

Semiotic analysis based on ontological framework revealed that there is a marked difference between P-1 and P-2, P-1 and P-3, P-1 and P-4, and P-1 and P-5 about the difference in semantic quality based on their interpretability value. Based on their relevance values, we discovered that there is a considerable difference in pragmatic quality between P-1 and P-3, P-1 and P-4, and P-1 and P-5. It was discovered that there is a considerable difference in social quality between P-1 and P-3 based on their authority value, and between P-1 and P-4 based on their authority and historical value. We observed there is a significant difference between P-2 and P-3, P-2 and P-4, and P-2 and P-5, about differences in pragmatic quality based on their relevance value. Furthermore, we found that P-2 and P-3 differ significantly in social quality based on their authority value. It was also noticed that there is a considerable difference between P-2 and P-4 in terms of social quality based on their power and historical significance. It was noticed that there is a weightage-wise difference between P-3 and P-4, regarding the difference in social quality based on their historical value. Additionally, there is a difference observed between P-4 and P-5 in terms of social authority and historical importance. Please see [Table 2](#) for detailed results.

The semiotic qualities were different among the paintings when statistical comparisons were made among the five selected paintings using SPSS followed by the chi-square test and Z-test. There is significant mean variation observed in case of syntactic qualities among the five paintings due to their characteristic feature [$\chi^2(4) = 13.135, p = 0.011$]. When syntactic quality was compared between painting No.1 (*please see P-1*) and painting No. 4 (*please see P-4*) a significant mean difference between the two paintings due to different semiotic characteristics including syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and social qualities [$Z(4) = -2.121, p = 0.034$]. Semiotic quality was also compared between painting No.2 (*please see P-2*) and painting No. 4 (*please see P-4*) a significant mean difference was observed between the two paintings due to differences in semiotic characteristics including syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and social qualities [$Z(4) = -2.070, p = .038$]. We noticed significant mean variations in *social qualities* among the five paintings due to their characteristic feature in terms of authority and history [$\chi^2(4) = 16.394, p = 0.003$]. When a pairwise comparison of *social quality* was conducted, significant differences in *overall semiotic quality* were observed between painting No.1 and painting No.4 [$Z(4) = -2.060, p = .039$], between painting No.2 and painting No.4 [$Z(4) = -2.060, p = .039$], between painting No.3 and painting No.4 [$Z(4) = -2.121, p = .034$], and, between painting No.4 and painting No.5 [$Z(4) = -2.041, p = .041$]. we also noted that there is a significant mean variation of *overall semiotic quality* (Syntactic, Semantic, Pragmatic, and Social qualities) among the five paintings due to their characteristic feature [$\chi^2(4) = 14.144, p = 0.007$]. When pairwise comparison of *overall semiotic quality* were conducted, significant differences in *overall semiotic quality* were observed between painting 1 (P-1) and painting 4 (P-4) [$Z(4) = -2.032, p = .042$], between painting No.1 and painting No.5 [$Z(4) = -2.041, p = .041$], between painting No. 2 painting No.4 [$Z(4) = -2.023, p = .043$], and, between painting No.3 and painting No.4 [$Z(4) = -2.023, p = .043$].

P-1 P-2 P-3 P-4 P-5

Figure 1. P-1: Emperor Jahangir weighs Prince Khurram; P-2: Attempt to assassinate Akbar at Delhi; P-3: The Child Akbar Recognizes his mother; P-4: The Book of Pigeons; P-5: Hamza's spy Basu beheads an enemy and gains entry to the castle of Acre.

5. Discussion

The primary purpose of this study was to conduct a semiotic analysis of Indian Mughal paintings with a particular focus on paintings employing a flat perspective to unfold the semiotic codes and conventions inherent in Indian Mughal paintings. The results indicate a few key findings – 1) significant diversity in the semiotic qualities of Mughal dynasty paintings, including syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and social aspects; 2) each painting was found to possess a unique semiotic fingerprint, indicating individuality in artistic expression and cultural influences. The study highlight the interconnectedness of semiotic dimensions, emphasizing the importance of analyzing syntactic, semantic, pragmatic, and social qualities in conjunction for a comprehensive understanding of artworks. Social and historical contexts significantly influenced the semiotic expression of the paintings, reflecting variations in social qualities such as authority and historical significance. This highlights the impact of societal norms and historical events on artistic representation. Comparative analysis played a crucial role in identifying significant differences between paintings, revealing subtle nuances in their semiotic qualities and enhancing the depth of analysis.

Table 3. Semiotic Quality and Key-element Relationships of all Selected Paintings.

Painting No.	Featured Semiotic Quality	Depictive Elements
P-1	$EI \times bel.3;$ $PR \times bp2.3;$ $OA \times bol.3;$ $OB \times bo2.3$	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interpretability is defined by subjects and objects presented in the painting as per the theme 2. The cultural <i>relevance</i> is represented by the event depicted through gathering, the primitive weighing machine, currency, ornaments and other relevant goods. 3. The <i>authority</i> is represented through the King in the court (Mughal court) and his advisors, currency, ornaments, and other relevant goods. 4. The painting conveys the message about the event (weighing ceremony of Prince Khurram) a kind of event used to organize during the Mughal kingdom, which is historic.
P-2	$PR \times bp2.3;$ $OA \times bol.3;$ $OB \times bo2.3$	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The painting is related to the Attempt to assassinate Akbar in Delhi. The relevance theme provides every aspect related to the assassinate like the attacking movements of the killer, weapons-like showed, spears, and shields are shown to represent the pragmatic relevance. 2. The authority is represented through the King in the court (Mughal court) and his throne. 3. The painting conveys the message about the event of Attempt to assassinate Akbar in Delhi, which is historic.

P-3	OB × b_{02.3}	1. The painting conveys the message about the event- <i>The Child Akbar Recognises his mother, that is a historical event.</i>
P-4	-	None of the quality expressed at a high level of semiotic quality
P-5	OA × b_{01.3} + OB × b_{02.3}	1. The painting depicts the power of the kingdom; Basu beheads an enemy and gains entry castle of Acre. The killing event and gadwalls depict the authority 2. The painting conveys the message about the event- Basu beheads an enemy and gains entry castle of Acre, <i>which is a historical event.</i>

The semantic variations indicate the several symbolic meanings embedded in the artworks, and the syntactic variations indicate distinct compositional methods and visual structures. Social features provide insights into the social circumstances depicted in the paintings, while pragmatic variations allude to a variety of practical and contextual implications. This comprehensive study highlights both the complexity of Mughal art and the crucial role that semiotic analysis plays in comprehending the rich cultural significance and multiple meanings that are present in these works of art. Understanding these nuanced semiotic characteristics helps us better appreciate the variety and diversity of artistic expression within the Mughal aesthetic tradition by shedding light on the complex web of meanings that these paintings reflect. The complex interrelationship between aesthetic style and syntactic composition is further demonstrated by these paired comparisons. The stark discrepancies in syntactic quality between paintings with recognizable distinguishing qualities indicate that the artistic decisions and expressions of the creators have a direct bearing on the structural components of their works. (Schapiro, 1969). It is vital to remember that artistic style encompasses a broad range of elements, making it a challenging component in assessing syntactic quality. (Tooby & Cosmides, 2001; Hellman, 1977).

The most salient finding of the study is the presence of significant mean variations in the syntactic qualities. This suggests that the differences between the paintings are not merely superficial, but are rooted in their fundamental creative composition and structure. In this respect (Tinio, 2013), highlights that the differences between the paintings come from the underlying creative composition and structural features rather than merely their outward look.

The individual identifying traits of each painting may be responsible for the observed significant mean syntactic quality disparities across the five paintings. The tremendous diversity of creative expression techniques, styles, and themes can have a substantial influence on a painting's syntactic qualities. Creating an artwork is turning a notion into a tangible embodiment, like a painting. This process is intricate and reliant on the social and creative circumstances as well as the artist's prior experiences, knowledge of the arts, talents, and motivations. The variety of approaches, supplies, and subject matter at the artist's disposal further brightens the complexity. However, several studies have shown procedures and stages that are common to the production of several artworks (Mace & Ward, 2002). Our study has explained the notable mean differences in syntactic properties that were seen across the five paintings owing to their distinctive attributes. The study reveals that the syntactic composition of Mughal paintings is influenced by artistic style and structural characteristics, highlighting the diverse creative expression and cultural, religious, and societal contexts that shaped the flat perspective. However, due to the vastness of this subject, the research may not encompass an exhaustive analysis of all paintings with a flat perspective but provide a representative and insightful exploration of the chosen artworks. Furthermore, the study may not delve extensively into conservation or technical aspects related to these paintings. Future studies in this area may dive into the subtleties of how various creative decisions materialize in the visual language of art and investigate the precise parts of defining characteristics that impact syntactic attributes. Understanding these connections can improve our perception of art and offer insightful information about how artists think and create.

6. Conclusion

The outcomes of the semiotic analysis show that the chosen Flat Perspective paintings from the Mughal period do not all have the same syntactic properties. Instead, these properties varied widely among the paintings, illuminating the unique traits and the aesthetics of each piece of art. The study provided light on the complex semiotic aspects of Mughal art by showing how bow parts within the paintings interacted with one another and with cultural surroundings. This indicates the significance of considering the ontological framework and semiotic elements while assessing the value and the significance of Mughal artworks with a Flat Perspective. Mughal paintings with a Flat Perspective serve as a reminder of the need to go beyond a cursory or generalized analysis of these works of art and instead take into account the complex interplay of visual elements, cultural symbolism, and historical context that determine the syntactic qualities of each painting. This more subtle approach may offer a deeper comprehension of Mughal art and its importance. In summary, the conclusion

highlights the richness and diversity of paintings from the Mughal era that use flat perspective. It also emphasizes the necessity for a sophisticated evaluation and interpretation of these paintings that takes into accounts both their distinctive syntactic characteristics and cultural context. Deeper insights into the visual vocabulary and creative preferences of the Mughal painters during this time will come from more studies in this field. It also underscores the need for a sophisticated evaluation and interpretation of these paintings considering their distinctive syntactic characteristics and cultural context.

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